

Phytoconstituents of *Scoparia dulcis* induces alteration of Hoxa 10 expression in uterus during periimplantation period of gestation in mice

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Scoparia dulcis Linn. has been used by certain communities of Arunachal Pradesh and Assam to alleviate various reproductive disorders. Hoxa10 is one of the prime transcription factors in regulating embryo implantation and development. However precise role of this transcription factor during early gestation period is yet to be addressed. The present study investigated the effects of crude extract of *Scoparia dulcis* (CESD) on embryo implantation and Hoxa10 expression during periimplantation period. Threshold dose was determined by multiple dose administration of CESD. The threshold dose of methanolic CESD was orally administered to the female mice during day 1-day 6 of gestation. Spatio-temporal expression of the Homeobox transcription factor Hoxa10 was studied using immunofluorescence technique and western blot. The crude extract induced the structural aberration of uterine and embryonic histology during periimplantation period. Evident changes in embryo size and orientation has been observed. Drastic reduction of expression of Hoxa10 was seen in the CESD treated female uteri. CESD contains potential phytochemicals capable of modulating the Estrogen receptors (ER) causing reduced expression of Hoxa10 in the target tissues. Any discrepancy in the Hoxa10 expression through the administration of the CESD can cause abrogation of embryo development and failure of viable pregnancy. The CESD may be a potent agent which may be used during post implantation period for safe termination of undesired pregnancy.

Key words: *Scoparia dulcis*; Phytochemicals; Pregnancy; Implantation.